

Project Acronym - Number: CE4Plastics - 101059423

Project title: Capillary electrophoresis as a main pillar for the characterisation of nanoplastics released from single-use and reusable plastic drinking bottles

Deliverable 1.1

Data Management Plan

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History of records			
Version	Date	Reason	Revised by
1.0	03/02/2023	First draft	Bart Doms (VITO)
1.1	10/02/2023	Second draft	Bart Doms (VITO)
1.2	17/02/2023	Final version	Stefan Voorspoels and Kristof Tirez (VITO)

Dissemination level		
PU	Fully open (automatically posted online on the Project Results platforms)	X
SEN	Limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	
EU	EU classified under Decision 2015/444	

1. Introduction

The purpose of the Data Management Plan (DMP) herein described is to explain how data will be handled throughout the project. The FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse) will be followed in order to ensure adherence to best practices in acquisition, creation, storage, use, archiving and deletion of any data and information obtained or generated during the project. In particular, data governance procedures will be put in place to ensure compliance with regulatory requirements and General Data Protection Regulations (GDPR). This plan will include information on research data treatment during and after the end of the project, what kind of data will be gathered and treated, what methodology standards will be applied, whether data will be shared or published in open-access mode, and how data will be curated, even after finishing the project.

CE4Plastics project will follow the open science policy of Horizon Europe, as detailed in the Programme Regulation (Art. 10 and 35(3)) and in the General Model Grant Agreement (Art. 17). The key elements of the open science approach are: i) Open Access will be provided to all scientific publications of the project results ('gold' or 'gold hybrid' access). The articles published via 'green' access, will be deposited via the repository Zenodo - an OpenAIRE compliant repositior; (ii) All data or other results needed for validation of conclusions of peer-reviewed publications will be granted open access through Zenodo; (iii) Responsible research data management is envisioned that is in line with FAIR principles (findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable); (iv) Promote the engagement in other open science practices, such as participation in open peer-review, sharing of pre-prints (Zenodo, arXiv or bioRxiv) and sharing of protocols, workflows and analytic scripts

2. Data Summary

Dataset Name	Description	New or reused	Digital or Physical	Only for digital data			Only for physical data
				Digital Data Type	Digital Data format	Digital data volume (MB/GB/TB)	Physical volume
Sample Data	Information about sample collection (date, time, analysts involved, matrix type, labelling, etc).	New	Physical				1000 samples of 10 cm ³
Protocol data	Standard operating procedures describing laboratory directions to perform experiments and device management.	New	Digital	Textual object	.pdf	< 100 MB	

Experimental data	Information about standard operating procedures employed in the laboratory for experiment performing and sample preparation methodologies, together with location of raw data for injections.	New	Digital	Textual object	.csv	< 100 MB	
Raw data	Electropherograms Spectral data Correlograms Sample lists	New	Digital	Visual object	.csv, .hdf5, .txt, .jpg	< 500 MB	
Result data	Details about parameter analysed for every sample, i.e. particle concentration, migration time, hydrodynamic diameter, etc.	New	Digital	Textual object	.csv, .txt	< 100 MB	

Evaluation data	Data treatment for the aforementioned raw data derived from instrumental analysis for every sample.	New	Digital	Visual object	.csv, .jpg	< 1 TB	
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What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

The main goal of CE4Plastics project is to advance the-state-of-the-art approaches for identification and quantification of nanoplastics (NPs) by developing methodologies based on capillary electrophoresis (CE) for characterisation of NPs released from single-use and reusable plastic water bottles. The said technique has been employed with a diode-array detector (DAD) so far, and it is intended to be coupled with fluorescent detection or identification techniques namely inductively-coupled plasma-mass spectrometry in single-particle mode (spICP-MS) and mass spectrometry (MS). Dynamic light scattering (DLS) will also be of use for result confirmation of sample preparation procedures. Particularly, the aim of the different data collected and summarised in the table above is to follow the analytical procedure from the very first step to the final data curation and interpretation, therefore traceability will be guaranteed and any procedural error will be likely to be monitored at all times throughout the project.

What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect?

The workflow depicted on Figure 1 shows the metadata sources derived from the analytical procedures performed in the laboratory.

Figure 1. Flow diagram depicting practical examples of metadata sources as a result of the experimental work performed in the laboratory, including data collection from the analytical equipment.

Apart from the aforementioned metadata to be processed throughout the project, dissemination activities will generate presentations (.pptx extension file), written communications to conferences (.docx format), articles or audiovisual material (.jpg, .png, .avi, .mp4 formats) to be shared on the project website, and formal documentation related with project deliverables, such as scientific papers and reports (.docx and .pdf formats).

Will you re-use any existing data and how?

It is foreseen that both sample metadata, protocol and experimental metadata will be of use to peers working in the laboratory in order to reproduce similar results under the same conditions described for sample collection and experimental procedure, which provide directions to be followed by the analyst.

It is unlikely that the gathered raw data will be re-used, as they will be collected under certain instrumental conditions that may vary from one laboratory to another or even in the same work atmosphere. Only similar results may be obtained, even if identical conditions are reproduced.

What is the origin of the data?

All data related with sample, protocol and experimental metadata will be generated from the analyst work in the laboratory on a daily basis. The aforementioned devices available in the laboratory at VITO will be the main source for all data originated from instrumental analysis, as measurements will result in the raw data and their subsequent evaluation.

What is the expected size of the data?

The total data amount is estimated to be around 2 terabytes.

To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

The usefulness of the generated data might be exploited by peers working on the same or similar scientific objectives, plastic-bottle manufacturers committed with the environment, analytical instrumentation companies and some statistics may be provided to the public opinion in order to raise consciousness about the presence of nanoplastics in bottled water.

3. FAIR data

a. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata, identifiable and locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers)?

The model established by Flemish Open Science Board (FOSB) will permit to get access to all data gathered throughout the project. FOSB unites all Flemish stakeholders in a shared vision for the future with regard to Open Science and European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), and, supported by technical working groups, advises the policy on steps to be taken to fully integrate Flanders into the international Open Science landscape. Its aim is to gradually reach 100% open access, make data sharing the default (with opt outs) and invest.

What naming conventions do you follow?

For data analysis, the convention is [YYYYMMDD]-[Project No]-[Affiliation]-[WP#]-[T###]-[version nr]-[keyword]-[keyword]. As regards data to be published, Digital Object Identifiers (DOI) will be employed. DOI is a managed system for persistent identification of content on digital networks. It can be used to identify physical, digital, or abstract entities. The identifiers (DOI names) resolve to data specified by the registrant and use an extensible metadata model to associate descriptive and other elements of data with the DOI name. The DOI system is implemented through a federation of registration agencies, under policies and common infrastructure provided by the International DOI Foundation, which developed and controls the system. DOI system provides identifiers which are persistent, unique, resolvable, and interoperable and so useful for management of content on digital networks in automated and controlled ways.

Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Keywords will be provided in a comprehensive way (e.g. table, list) in order to promote their re-use.

Do you provide clear version numbers?

Version numbers will be provided with at most two digits (e.g. v1.1).

What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

Metadata standards are defined by FOBS convention.

b. Making data openly accessible

Which data produced and/or used in the project will be made openly available as the default? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from voluntary restrictions.

As the default, all data related with scientific publications, dissemination activities, training sessions and deliverables will be made openly available. Raw data will be available on request. Due to practical aspects, raw data will be stored on the internal network drive, and every person may have access in response to their enquiry.

How will the data be made accessible (e.g. by deposition in a repository)?

All data will be accessible via Zenodo, an open-access repository.

What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Standard software tools at user level will permit to access data, as they will typically be displayed in universal formats, namely .csv, .txt, etc.

Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

A Commercial-off-the-shelf (COTS) software may be included to access data.

Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No, since the software is a commercial product.

Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited? Preference should be given to certified repositories which support open access where possible.

Raw data will be deposited at VITO installations and may be accessed by every person who request it. Zenodo will be the certified repository where open data will be deposited.

Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository?

No, as no sensitive data will be used.

If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?

Not applicable.

Is there a need for a data access committee?

Not applicable.

Are there well described conditions for access (i.e. a machine readable license)?

This project is subject to a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Licence (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

By means of a Zenodo protocol that allows for an authentication and authorisation procedure.

c. Making data interoperable

Are the data produced in the project interoperable, that is allowing data exchange and re-use between researchers, institutions, organisations, countries, etc. (i.e. adhering to standards for formats, as much as possible compliant with available (open) software applications, and in particular facilitating re-combinations with different datasets from different origins)?

Data will be available in universal formats, namely .csv or .txt. Therefore, any standard software tool will permit to open any type of data, no matter their source.

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?

Data vocabularies are coming from the COTS software. FOSB will permit metadata to be available.

Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in your data set, to allow interdisciplinary interoperability?

Yes, unique identifiers.

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies?

Ontologies for CE, DLS, ICP-MS and MS will be sought in such a way to make data interoperable.

d. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?

A Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Licence will be of use. Creative Commons helps overcome legal obstacles to the sharing of knowledge and creativity to address the world's most pressing challenges. Every person and organisation in the world are provided with a free, simple, and standardised way to grant copyright permissions for creative and academic works; ensure proper attribution; and allow others to copy, distribute, and make use of those works.

When will the data be made available for re-use? If an embargo is sought to give time to publish or seek patents, specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

Data will be made available when gathered and compiled on Zenodo, followed by publication in Open Research Europe. Results will be then available for peers and the general public. If a patent has been registered with some data, these will only be accessible once patent rights are expired.

Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.

The Creative Commons licence employed will allow every person for data reuse.

How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

At least 10 years, period after which a long-term reuse will be considered.

Are data quality assurance processes described?

Data obtaining follows quality assurance standards established by standard operating procedures in the laboratory, analytical parameters for method development and validation, and applicability to the actual samples so as to ensure accuracy, consistency and uniqueness.

4. Allocation of resources

What are the costs for making data FAIR in your project?

It is foreseen that no costs will be directly involved in making data FAIR, as the project is fully funded by EU.

How will these be covered? Note that costs related to open access to research data are eligible as part of the Horizon 2020 grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions).

The project budget is foreseen to cover the aforementioned costs.

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

VITO, as the lead beneficiary for the project, will be in charge for data management.

Are the resources for long term preservation discussed (costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)?

All data will be available for a minimum period of 10 years counted from the project end date.

5. Data security

What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)?

All data will be housed on internal servers whose access is locked by username and password. Besides, Zenodo repository provides a high degree of data security via creation of duplicate data sets at disk servers with different location.

Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation?

Yes, according to security policy followed by VITO.

6. Ethical aspects

No ethical matters are addressed in this project, since neither animals nor individuals will be subject to experiments.

7. Other issues

No additional issues are foreseen to be dealt with in this document.